

easily be explained on the assumption that in the mesomorphic state seven or eight molecules are associated to form a complex molecule (for then the parachor decrease will be $7 \times 14.4/8$ or 12.6 units, Sidgwick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1461). The variations in the parachor at temperatures above the melting point may be explained on the assumption that the molecules are still slightly associated, and this association diminishes with the rise of temperatures; with azoxybenzene this phenomenon is also observed.

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Negative Ferric Hydroxide Sol. A Modified Method of its Preparation.

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Powis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 818) describes a simple method for the preparation of negative ferric hydroxide sol. This sol contains, however, an excess of alkali which evidently has a stabilising influence on it. Our attempt was directed to replace the superfluous alkali by another electrolyte, neutral in character, and possessing at the same time a stabilising influence on the sol. We required such a neutral sol for extracting uranium-X from uranyl salts. In this attempt we have found a few electrolytes possessing stabilising action. They are characterised from the other (similarly examined) electrolytes in giving iron salts, stable in an alkaline medium. It is generalised therefrom that an electrolyte, which gives an iron salt, stable in an alkaline medium, has a stabilising action on negative ferric hydroxide sol.

The substances found to possess a stabilising action are potassium citrate, potassium tartrate, potassium carbonate, potassium sulphide, sodium phosphate and sodium silicate. The citrate and the tartrate

are already known to possess such stabilising action with regard to negative ferric hydroxide sol. The neutrality in all cases has been tested with litmus. The sol obtained with potassium sulphide was, however, faintly alkaline.

The nature of the different sols have been tested by their behaviour as regards precipitation towards a normal solution of barium chloride, lanthanum nitrate or potassium sulphate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For preparing a sol according to Powis (*loc. cit.*), to 150 c.c. of $N/100$ -alkali hydroxide solution, 100 c.c. of $N/100$ - FeCl_3 solution were added drop by drop, and the alkali hydroxide continuously shaken. It is, however, possible to add more of ferric chloride solution to the alkali hydroxide, but by this addition at a definite stage the ferric hydroxide present in the sol condition, is thrown out of the solution. There exists, therefore, a definite ratio (as will be evident from Fig. 1) between the amounts of the alkali and the ferric chloride used up when the precipitation phenomenon occurs. If the stabilising electrolytes be added before introducing ferric chloride, the above ratio changes and the precipitation occurs at a later stage; by increasing the amount of a stabiliser precipitation may be made to take place just after the equivalent amount of ferric chloride has been added. There exists, therefore, a definite limit in the amount of a stabiliser, which enables an equivalent amount of iron to remain in the sol condition. And if more than this limiting amount be taken at the beginning and then the equivalent amount of ferric chloride be added, the required neutral sol will be obtained.

With substances possessing no stabilising action, the definite ratio between the amounts of alkali hydroxide and ferric chloride does not change, even if their amount be increased. The titration values indicating the definite ratio between the amounts of alkali hydroxide and ferric chloride are given below.

TABLE I.

KOH ($N/100$).	FeCl_3 ($N/100$).	KOH ($N/100$).	FeCl_3 ($N/100$).
10. c.c.	9.2 c.c.	60 c.c.	52.0 c.c.
20	17.5	70	59.2
30	26.6	80	68.2
40	35	90	76.9
50	45	100	85.5

The graph representing these values is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 100 c.c., 60 c.c., 30 c.c., and 10 c.c.

Table II records the titration values obtained with K_2S showing that definite ratio mentioned is changed progressively by employing a stabiliser. A similar course of change was followed in the cases of other stabilisers.

TABLE II.

1 C.c. of K_2S soln. contains 2.09 mg. $\equiv$ 20 drops. $N/100-KOH$ soln. taken = 10 c.c. $FeCl_3$ soln. used = $N/100$.

K_2S (drops).	...	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
$FeCl_3$ required (c.c.)	...	9.20	9.35	9.50	9.65	9.80	9.90	10.00

Fig. 2 shows the course of change found for the different amounts of potassium hydroxide in the case of potassium sulphide. In Fig. 2, the deficit noticed, *i.e.* the difference from the equivalent amount of

ferric chloride, has been plotted against the amount of the stabiliser for the different amounts of potassium hydroxide solution employed, namely, 10 c.c., 30 c.c., 60 c.c. and 100 c.c.

Table III records the titration values obtained with K_2S where such stabilising action was not found.

TABLE III.

1 C.c. K_2SO_4 soln. contains 5 mg. = 20 drops.. 10 C.c. $N/100$ KOH solution taken.

Amount of K_2SO_4 (in drops).	0	1	2	3	4	10
$N/100$ - $FeCl_3$ required (c.c.)	9.20	9.15	9.20	9.20	9.20	9.20

To ensure the absence of any stabilising influence, similar titrations were carried out with different amounts of potassium hydroxide solution. Besides potassium sulphate, the substances found to have no stabilising action under these conditions are, sodium succinate and sulphocyanide, ferricyanide, ferrocyanide and indigo-tetrasulphonate of potassium.

Comparative Stabilisation.

The condition of the stability of the sol (as we have inferred) is that the iron salt given by a substance possessed of a stabilising influence, should be a stable one in an alkaline medium. But it may be expected that the negative radicals of these stabilising substances should have an influence on the stabilisation and a comparative study of this influence is feasible following the method of investigation we have adopted. For this purpose an accurate estimation of the amount of the negative radicals in the various substances was made in the following way: Carbonate, citrate, and tartrate radicals were estimated indirectly from an estimation of potassium as potassium sulphate; the sulphide was estimated indirectly from the amount of potassium hydroxide taken for its preparation; the phosphate radical was estimated from ferric phosphate, taking a known amount of ferric chloride; and finally, the silicate was estimated from the amount of silica obtained and also indirectly by removing silica with hydrofluoric and sulphuric acids.

It has been shown that the minimum amount of the stabilising substances, required to bring the ratio between the amounts of alkali hydroxide and ferric chloride to unity, corresponds to a definite stability of the sol produced. Under this condition the amounts of

various negative radicals should give an idea of the degree of influence exercised by them. In Table IV the amount of different negative radicals found for the different amounts of potassium hydroxide is given.

TABLE IV.

$N/100$ -KOH sol. $N/100$ - FeCl_3 soln. used

Radical,	Amount in mgs. corresponding to KOH solution taken in			
	10 c.c.	30 c.c.	60 c.c.	100 c.c.
Citrate	0.3521 mg.	0.7747 mg.	1.4085 mg.	2.8874 mg.
Tartrate	0.4695	1.0955	2.0343	3.2865
PO_4'''	0.3212	0.6424	1.2045	2.7302
SiO_3''	0.3302	0.7338	1.4680	2.642
S''	0.1815	0.3629	0.9073	2.1171
CO_3''	0.7584	1.4220	2.8440	6.3516

The above figures by themselves convey no idea about the comparative influence. If however they are expressed (*vide* Table V) in terms of gram-ion, an idea of the degree of influence exercised by the radicals becomes apparent.

TABLE V.

Radical. Amount in g. ions corresponding to the amount of KOH soln. $\times 10^6$ in

	10 c.c.	30 c.c.	60 c.c.	100 c.c.
Citrate	1.862	4.099	7.45	15.28
Tartrate	3.173	7.401	13.74	22.2
PO_4'''	3.382	6.673	12.68	28.74
SiO_3''	4.328	9.618	19.24	34.63
S''	5.662	11.32	28.30	66.04
CO_3''	12.64	23.7	47.4	105.9

The degree of influence exercised follows the order arranged as, citrate > tartrate > phosphate > silicate > sulphide > carbonate. Fig. 3 represents a better manifestation of this comparison. Curves in Fig. 3 show that the amount of the stabiliser, except in the case of the tartrate, is not strictly proportional to the amount of potassium hydroxide taken.

Fig 3.

Curves 1-6 refer respectively to $\text{CO}_3^{''}$, $\text{S}^{''}$, $\text{SiO}_3^{''}$, $\text{PO}_4^{''}$, tartrate and citrate ions.

The stability has also been examined from two other different standards. In one case the time required for coagulation with a $N/100$ solution of lanthanum nitrate, has been noted. This has been done with the sols prepared with double the amount of the stabilising substances, corresponding to the data in Tables VI and VII. The data given below refer to 10 c.c. of the sol in each case. We should mention that a consistent value of the time required for coagulation, is obtained only when the sol is kept rotating since the addition of lanthanum nitrate.

TABLE VI.

La(NO ₃) ₃ .	Time required for coagulation with			
	Citrate.	Tartrate.	Phosphate.	Silicate.
10 drops	38 sec.	51 sec.	21 sec	37 sec.
8	49	60	33	25
6	69	75	57	21
4	No coagulation noticed on that day.			19
				70

TABLE VII.

La(NO ₃) ₃ .	Time required for coagulation with		
	Sulphide.	Carbonate.	Powis' sol.
10 drops	14.5 sec.	13 sec.	31 sec.
8	18	16	40
6	22	18	51
4	27	25	69
2	35	29.9	142

Data in Tables VI and VIII show that the order of stability mentioned is practically maintained. The sol containing the silicate behaves rather abnormally, the time required for coagulation decreasing at first and then increasing as the amount of lanthanum nitrate is progressively decreased. We may point it out that lanthanum nitrate will give insoluble compounds with the above stabilising substances; and for this very reason it cannot be an ideal electrolyte for noting coagulation. But a better substitute (having a polyvalent positive radical) will be difficult to obtain. The data given for the sol prepared according to Powis will show that the sol is nearly as stable as the one containing the citrate.

The other standard we have mentioned, is the preservability, *i.e.*, the period till the sol is coagulated if left by itself. We give below the period observed in the different cases.

TABLE VIII.

Stabiliser.	Period.	Stabiliser.	Period.
Silicate	15 days	Citrate	about 5 days
Tartrate	9 to 10 days	Sulphide	6 to 7 hours
Phosphate	5 to 6 days	Carbonate	4 to 5 hours
		Powis' sol.	about 4 days

We shall find that in respect of spontaneous coagulation, the previous order has not been maintained. We have also seen that the sol prepared with citrate, can be preserved for a longer period in winter than in summer.